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ABSTRACT BOOK

Posters

Outcomes of Two Stage Exchange Arthroplasty of Hip and Knee for Prosthetic Joint Infection. A pre-formed Antibiotic-Loaded Acrylic Cement Spacer for Hip and Knee.

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Introduction: Pre-formed antibiotic-loaded acrylic cement spacers (pALACS) for hip and knee contribute to comfortable treatment of chronic periprosthetic joint infection (PJI) of the hip and knee in two-stage replacement arthroplasty.

Methods: In the study 48 patients had undergone two-stage replacement surgical procedure due to the chronic PJI. P-ALACS spacers for hip or knee were introduced during the first stage of surgical procedure. Patients' treatment process had been monitored for 120 months (range 4-120 months). The timing of reimplantation was based on laboratory values (C-reactive protein values <10) and clinical improvements..

Results: In the first act of revision surgery were implanted 33 (68,75%) pALACS for the hip and 15 (31,25%) pALACS for the knee. Two patients (4,16%) with the hip pALACS has been still awaiting the second surgery pending the periprosthetic infection sufficient reduction. In five patients (10,4%) with knee pALACS after the first act of revision surgery pALACS was removed and they had to undergo knee arthrodesis. 41 patients (85,4%) had successfully undergone two-stage replacement arthroplasty with the implementation of the knee or hip pALACS, respectively, in the first stage surgery.

Conclusions: Implementation of the pre-formed ALACS appeared effective in treatment of infection and simplified the second act of surgery - reimplantation.

Keywords:

Chronic periprosthetic joint infection of the hip and knee, pre-formed ALACS, two-stage exchange arthroplasty.